

Group on Earth Observations
Community of Practice for Ocean
Observations
(OO CoP)

Bob Houtman
National Science Foundation

GEO OO CoP Background

Community Meetings

NSF Sponsored Workshop Bremen 2009

OceanObs 2009 Venice

GEOSS Workshop Seattle 2010

Identified Need

A forum for ocean observing leaders and users to look at key issues

GEO OO CoP Background

Response

Terms of Reference drafted and revised
with community input

Presented to GEO UIC and OO CoP
approved in April 2011

GEO OO CoP

Terms of Reference

Purpose

Bring together leaders from differing observing system stakeholder organizations as a forum for improved coordination across observing systems

Further GEOSS principles and goals in the oceans and marine realm and support introduction of requirements, observations and practices

Address cross-cutting issues in oceanography that impact observing systems and their users

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Terms of Reference

Objectives

Facilitate implementation and coordination of ocean and marine observatories and observing programs and partnerships in regard to common monitoring goals and strategies

Support implementation of GEOSS principles to improve and enable continuity and sustainability of observing systems and open exchange of data and information

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Terms of Reference

Objectives

Stimulate capacity building in ocean and marine observations

Report on Progress and give advice to GEO on issues relating to observing the world oceans and seas

Disseminate this information to relevant communities concerned with and reliant upon global observing systems

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Terms of Reference

Working Methods

Operate primarily through electronic information exchange

One annual in-person meeting

Minutes published electronically within 2 weeks

Work closely with existing coordination bodies to avoid duplication, strengthen-expand existing mechanisms

Form task groups as needed

Coordinate with GEO Coastal Zone CoP

GEO OO CoP

Membership

Albert Fischer (Co-chair)-UNESCO (FR)

Bob Houtman (Co-chair)-NSF (US)

Simon Allen -CSIRO (AU)

Stewart Bernard-CSIR NRE (ZA)

Pierre Bahurel-Mercator/GMES (FR)

Jon Blower- NERC (UK)

Masao Fukasawa-JAMSTEC (JP)

Keith Haines-NERC (UK)

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Membership

Steve Hankin- NOAA (US)

Sissy Iona-Hellenic Data Cntr (GR)

Jay Pearlman-IEEE (US)

Peter Pissierssens-UNESCO (BE)

Iain Shepherd- European Commission (EU)

Ariel Troisi-Jefe DeprtmnOceanografia (AR)

Christoph Waldmann-U Bremen (DE)

Zdenka Willis-NOAA (US)

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Terms of Reference

Overall Plan of Activities

Support GEOSS Strategic Target:

- 1.1 Architecture: “Achieve sustained operation, continuity and interoperability of existing and new systems that provide essential environmental observations and information, including GEOSS Common Infrastructure (GCI) that facilitates access to, and use of, these observations and information”

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Support GEOSS Strategic Target:

1.2 Data Management: “Provide for a shared, easily accessible, timely, sustained stream of comprehensive data of documented quality, as well as metadata and information products, for informed decision making”

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Support GEOSS Strategic Target:

2.3 Climate: “Achieve effective and sustained operation of the global climate observing system and reliable delivery of climate information of a quality needed for predicting, mitigating and adapting to climate variability and change, including better understanding of the global carbon cycle”

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Support GEOSS Strategic Target:

2.9 Weather: “Close critical gaps in meteorological and related ocean observations, and enhance observational and information capabilities for the protection of life and property, especially with regard to high-impact events, and in the developing world ”

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Support GEOSS Tasks:

AR-09-03c “enabling and improving the coordination of coastal/open-ocean observations and modelling initiatives, in support of a Global Ocean Observation System”

AR-09-03d”achieving a complete and stable Global Observing System”

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Terms of Reference

Specific actions planned

Identify steps for:

Further stimulating national commitments to ocean and marine observing systems..

Facilitating open exchange of data and information and in demonstration of societal value of ocean and marine observations

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Terms of Reference

Specific actions planned

Provide inputs to GEO and the GEO Work Plan

Create/update existing compendia of current and future requirements and support for ocean and marine observing systems

Review current systems' capabilities and prioritize strategies for future developments to sustain existing systems and expand to meet current and future requirements

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Near-term Focus and Goals

Collaborative action in the flow of data from ocean observing systems through data management systems to scientific and operational users

Connection of ocean data streams to the GEOSS Common Infrastructure

Identification of how ocean data contributes to GEO Societal Benefit Areas

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Near-term Activities

Develop a “Charter” of initial specific issues

Identify specific activities to address each issue

OO CoP Kick-off teleconference 20 October

First face-to-face meeting at 2012 Ocean
Sciences Meeting

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Summary

GEO OO CoP established April 2011

Initial membership includes broad international participation by national organizations

Future membership may expand

Specific activities being identified

First teleconference 20 October 2011

First meeting February 2012 at Ocean Sciences